

High Mass X-ray Binaries: Future Perspectives

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It is difficult to make predictions, especially about the future.

Niels Bohr (~1948; probably...)

ASTROSAT

XMM

HXMT

SRG

NuSTAR

Chandra

Integral

NICER

Swift

Fermi

HMXB Science Case

Important HMXB scientific questions for the next 20 years

1. **What is the population of compact objects?**

black holes and neutron stars as tracers of stellar evolution; relationship to gravitational wave sources

2. **What is the nature of compact objects?**

black hole spins and their origin, structure of neutron stars,...

3. **What is the physics of the accretion flow?**

physics of accretion disks, jets, strongly magnetic sources,...

4. **What is the physics of stellar winds?**

Using X-rays to x-ray the circumstellar environment

Will address current status using three examples from INTEGRAL: [cyclotron lines](#), [polarization of hard X-rays in black hole X-ray binaries](#), and the “[INTEGRAL sources](#)”.

See later talks for much more

Accretion columns and cyclotron lines

Wind accretion in HMXB with strongly magnetized neutron stars: inside Alfvén surface: material falls along B-field lines onto polar caps
Rotation \Rightarrow Lighttower effect \Rightarrow X-ray pulsars

(Wilms 2014, after Davidson & Ostriker, 1973)

Acc

nes

IMXB with strongly magnetized inside Alfvén surface: material lines onto polar caps
 power effect \implies X-ray pulsars

(vidson & Ostriker, 1973)

Accretion columns and cyclotron lines

Cyclotron lines: inelastic scattering of photons off electrons in quantized orbits in strong B-field on magnetic poles of neutron stars.

⇒ neutron star B-field measurements

⇒ accretion columns

(V0322 + 53; Mowlavi et al., 2006)

Accretion columns and cyclotron lines

Cyclotron lines: inelastic scattering of photons off electrons in quantized orbits in strong B-field on magnetic poles of neutron stars.

⇒ neutron star B-field measurements

⇒ accretion columns

(V0332 + 53; Tsygankov et al., 2010)

Accretion columns and cyclotron lines

after P. Becker

Brightest sources: accretion column locally super-Eddington, radiation balances accreted matter

Accretion columns and cyclotron lines

after P. Becker

Brightish sources: Coulomb braking important, still some radiative pressure

Accretion columns and cyclotron lines

after P. Becker

Faint sources: Coulomb not sufficient, **gas mediated shock** somewhere above the surface...

Accretion columns and cyclotron lines

after P. Becker

really faint sources: accreted material smashes into the crust

Accretion columns and cyclotron lines

(Tsygankov et al., 2019)

(GX 304-1; Sokolova-Lapa et al., 2021)

Lowest \dot{M} : Fundamental change in structure of spectrum. Important for studying fundamental physics of matter in very strong B fields
see talk S. Tsygankov

Polarization

Cyg X-1 (Laurent et al., 2011)

Accretion Physics: Hard Tails in Black Holes

(Forot et al., 2007, Fig. 1)

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Polarization

Compton mode of IBIS instrument on *INTEGRAL*:
Compton scattering in IBIS layer, absorption in
PICsIT layer.

Forot et al. (2007, 2008); Dean et al. (2008):
Detection of both events allows

- to **reconstruct position to 12'** precision
- to measure **Compton scattering angle**:

$$\cos \theta_{\text{com}} = 1 - \frac{m_e c^2}{E_2} + \frac{m_e c^2}{E_1 + E_2}$$

- to measure **polarization**:

$$N(\bar{}) = S \cdot (1 + a_0 \cos(2\bar{} - 2\bar{}_0))$$

where a_0/a_{100} : deg. of polarization (a_{100} : nor-
malization, from GEANT), polarization angle:

$$PA = \Psi_0 - \frac{\pi}{2} + n\pi$$

(Forot et al., 2007, Fig. 1)

Polarization

(Laurent et al., 2011)

Compton mode for <400 keV data: polarization <20% (90% conf.)

Polarization

Compton mode for 400–2000 keV data: **polarization $67 \pm 30\%$, PA 40°**

SPI: $76\% \pm 15\%$, PA: $42^\circ \pm 3^\circ$; (Jourdain et al., 2012)

Interpretation: **synchrotron radiation, e.g., from jet or nonthermal corona?**

(Laurent et al., 2011; Zdziarski et al., 2012; Jourdain et al., 2012; Rodriguez et al., 2015; Cangemi et al., 2021)

Polarization

Cangemi et al., 2022, A&A, in press (arXiv:2210.08561)

Polarization

Cyg X-1: IXPE & balloons: very different behavior in the *soft* X-rays (e.g., Krawczynski et al., 2022, *Science*, in press) – illustrates importance of wide band polarization capabilities!

MAXI J1535-571, MAXI J1820+070 and MAXI J1348-630, 300-1000 keV band: **high polarization found for two sources**

Cangemi et al., 2022, *A&A*, in press (arXiv:2210.08561)

Populations: “INTEGRAL sources”

Distribution of HMXB in the Galaxy

Large fraction discovered with INTEGRAL.

Bodaghee et al. (2012), updated up to 2022 (Bodaghee, 2022, in prep.)

Populations: “INTEGRAL sources”

Norma arm with IBIS (Walter et al., 2003)

One of the main discoveries of INTEGRAL: “INTEGRAL sources”: population of compact objects embedded in very dense, cold stellar winds (Walter et al., 2003).

See talks this afternoon for more (L. Sidoli, E. Bozzo, S. Tsygankov,...)

Populations: “INTEGRAL sources”

Norma arm with IBIS (Walter et al., 2003)

Best spectral analysis of IGR J16318-4848 (Ballhausen et al., 2020): $N_{\text{H}} = 1.8 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, **strong dust absorption needed** to explain lack of Compton shoulder.

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Science Case

Observational needs for HMXB astrophysics in the next 20 years:

- **Population of compact objects:**
surveys
 - **Search and monitor transients:**
all sky (sr) monitors, large field of regard ($= \angle(\text{Sun, opt. axis})$)
 - **Nature of compact objects (e.g., spin):**
timing [μs , ms], spectroscopy [CCD sufficient]
 - **Accretion flow physics:**
polarization (not only in the soft X-rays!), timing, CCD-type E-res. spectroscopy [100 eV'ish], broad band coverage (0.5– \gtrsim 150 keV for reflection modeling, states, jet modeling), high collecting area
 - **Stellar wind physics, disk winds:**
high E-resolution (gratings/calorimeter) X-ray spectroscopy [few eV; **underutilized!**] and high collecting area
-

Approved Missions

Si-type resolution

(Fano – $\Delta E \sim 150$ eV at 5.9 keV, $R \sim 40$)

Gratings

($R \sim 1000$)

Si-type resolution

(Fano – $\Delta E \sim 150$ eV at 5.9 keV, $R \sim 40$)

Gratings & Microcalorimeters

($R \sim 1000$, $R \sim 70 \dots 4000$)

XRISM

100 ks generic X-ray binary; simulations for Hitomi

XRISM (X-ray imaging and spectroscopy mission): launch planned for Japanese fiscal year 2023: First microcalorimeter observations of X-ray binaries

Design: Hitomi microcalorimeter and CCD

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Design: Hitomi microcalorimeter and CCD , **no instrument >15 keV!**

Missions in preparation
not yet fully approved

Effective Areas

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Effective Areas

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Gratings & Microcalorimeters

($R \sim 1000$, $R \sim 70 \dots 4000$)

Effective Areas

Si-type

(Fano - $\Delta E \sim 15$)

calorimeters

(70 ... 4000)

Effective Areas

Si-type resolution

(Fano – $\Delta E \sim 150$ eV at 5.9 keV, $R \sim 40$)

Gratings & Microcalorimeters

($R \sim 1000$, $R \sim 70 \dots 4000$)

Mirrors

Science Instrument Module

Mirrors: Silicon pore optics (Cosine, Leiden)

© ESA, Cosine and the ACO team.

ESA/FA&Fab.

WFI

X-IFU

X-IFU

- 3840 TES
- operated at 50 mK
- Energy resolution 2.5 eV
- 5' field of view
- PI: D. Barret (IRAP, F)

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K

X-IFU

D. Barret (2022, Proc. SPIE)

Predicted spectral changes for photoionized wind around neutron star Vela X-1 for Athena (Hell et al., 2020, X-ray spectrometry 49, 218)

Diagnostics used:

- **Density** and **temperature diagnostics** (He-like ions, thermal broadening,...),
- **Elemental abundances**,
- **Velocities** via Doppler

and detailed **collisional ionization models**, **photoionization modeling**, and hybrid plasmas.

Requires: photoionization cross sections, gf-values, highly precise line energies, collisional ionization cross sections,... for all elements with $Z \lesssim 30$ and *all* ionization stages *and* astronomers who are specialists in the physics of highly ionized plasmas.

PI: K. Nandra (MPE, D)

Large Detector Array

- 40'x40
- 4x512x512 pxl
- <5ms/frame
- <10 μ s/row

Fast Detector

- defocused
- 64x64(/2) pxl
- <80 μ s/frame
- <2.5 μ s/row

Both

- 130 μ m x 130 μ m
- DEPFET technology

A. Rau

WFI

WFI

WFI: 1024×1024 Array of **DEPFET-Sensors** (active pixel sensors)
 μs time resolution...

energy resolution at theoretical (Fano) limit ($\sim 150 \text{ eV}$ at 6 keV).

BSc M. Rohe (Remeis/ECAP/FAU)

T. Dauser (Remeis/ECAP/FAU), N. Vulic (GSFC); based on XMM (Ms exposure, no data available outside of M31)

Athena WFI 5×5 mosaic of Andromeda (200 ks total)

X-ray population studies will be possible w/much less exposure time than today

\implies monitoring!...

China: eXTP

enhanced X-ray Timing and Polarimetry (eXTP):

proposal for Chinese Strategic Priority Program on Space Science (III) w/European contribution

- Spectroscopy Focusing Array: 0.9 m^2 at 1 keV
- Large Area Detector: 3.4 m^2 at 8 keV
- Polarimetry Focusing Array: 240 cm^2 at 6.4 keV
- Wide Field Monitor: 3 units (4 sr FoV)
- **Will be very important for HMXB research**

(see talk S.N. Zhang)

Missions proposals
“paper tigers”

ESA: M6 mission call

ESA M-class mission proposals, both large FoV monitoring missions:

THESEUS [see talk by L. Amati]

0.3–5 keV (0.5 sr FoV); 2 keV–10 MeV (2 sr FoV)

Amati et al., THESEUS yellow book

ESA: M6 mission call

ESA M-class mission proposals, both large FoV monitoring missions:
ASTROGAM: MeV mission, w trackers

HEX-P: “NuSTAR-squared”:

- extension to soft X-rays (CCD)
- harder coverage than NuSTAR (200 keV)
- good imaging (5''–10'')
- μs timing

Probably the probe concept most well suited for general HMXB research

NASA: Probes

Smith et al., 2017, SPIE

Arcus probe mission (Builds on 2017/2018 midex phase A study):

Soft X-ray mission w/transmission gratings; complementary to Athena

$\gg 450 \text{ cm}^2$, resolution $\Delta E/E > 2500$, no harder coverage

NASA: Probes

Strobe-X:

- WFM (4.1 sr)
- LAD (2–30 keV, 51000 cm², 10 μs timing
1 Crab = 156000 cps)
- XRCA (concentrators, 0.2–12 keV, ~22000 cm², 100 ns timing)

The mission design for bright sources, but lowish hard cutoff, no imaging

Summary

If successful, future missions will greatly extend current capabilities for HMXB research, promising new interesting results:

- Stellar evolution and population of compact objects
 - Nature of compact objects, physics of the extreme universe
 - Accretion flow physics
 - Stellar wind physics, disk winds
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But **we do have a serious problem:**

- **Programmatic outlook for many of the proposed missions is bleak** and that's even without taking into account the current earthquakes in the international order...
- **Approved real broad band coverage >10 keV almost completely missing:** the "MeV gap" really starts at 10 keV!
nothing real on the horizon yet except for COSI and Polar-2 \implies unlikely to change until the late 2030s

This is very ironic, considering the large investments made in TeV astronomy (CTA) and GW astronomy \implies **X-ray/gamma-ray follow up will be missing, although crucial for getting any physics out of these observations!**

Summary

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And, finally:

Don't forget: studying HMXB accretion physics has a real world applications, such as in the theory of garbage disposals...

Translation: *Black Hole: Looking for residual matter*

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